

Data stewardship for responsible sharing of public data – an analysis of stewardship models for better urban governance

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Extended Abstract

Previous and ongoing private sector use of public sector (personal) data, particularly for the generation of broader societal value, has been spurred most significantly by the fact that private sector bodies are well-equipped with solution-led computational tools. However, the resultant power dynamic from private sector use of public data has resulted in extractive, predatory and harmful consequences for communities at large. For public good efforts to avoid these outcomes, public-to-private sharing of data hinges on a few key aspects of sharing terms, definitions of community value, and the codification of frameworks for accountability and grievance mediation while making data available for use by private entities. This paper reviews existing models of sharing of public sector data, in the context of urban governance, for use by private sector and community organisations, and outlines how data stewardship can play a critical role in enshrining the interests, rights and agency of communities as we consider pathways between the private and public sector to make data available for social good.

There is much skepticism around the use of data (either privately or publicly held) by the private sector. Such skepticism stems from numerous cases of misuse of data for private gains, often coming at significant costs to individual citizens and communities. There have been numerous instances of gig work platforms, such as Uber, using data generated by workers on the platform to design algorithms to maximise corporate gains to the detriment of the workers. The mechanisms of control used by such platforms can result in low pay, social isolation, working irregular hours, overwork, sleep deprivation and a precarious employment arrangement with the looming threat of being blacklisted by the platform. Private sector institutions also make available data that can have disastrous consequences for the privacy and rights of individuals. For instance, location data from the mobile application Grindr was used to reveal that a Catholic Priest visited gay bars, leading to his resignation. Critically, despite being anonymised, the dataset could be used by members of the public to link a particular data point to an individual – leading to reidentification and loss of individual as well as group privacy. Private sector actors can also derive private benefit from open or public data at the cost of community interests. Regeneron, an American Pharmaceutical Company, created an Ebola treatment using genetic information sequenced from a Guinean Ebola survivor that was placed in an open-source database for free by a Germany research centre. Despite the Guinean government being the sovereign owner of the sequence data, they received no benefits from this, while Regeneron got more than US \$ 400 million in research and development commitments. With the treatment being given proprietary protections, the Guinean government were left to rely on benevolence either from the US government or Regeneron themselves for access to a treatment that could not have been synthesised without access to Guinean resources.

However, public data, if shared under the right conditions, with adequate safeguards, has immense potential in creating social good. Smart city initiatives, in locations such as Amsterdam, Barcelona, Brainport, and Rennes are all novel examples of how public sector data can be leveraged for public good while preserving the rights and interests of individuals

and communities. What is clear is that the sharing of public sector data with private sector for public good hinges on a few key aspects, including, but not limited to, the terms on which data is shared (the uses it can be put to, who it can then be shared with), the value that communities derive from data, and the codification of accountability to the public sector.

The positioning of citizens as central to data collection, sharing and use efforts can serve as a strong medium to embody these principles. As the DECODE project, piloted in Amsterdam and Barcelona, highlights, greater trust around smart city initiatives can be fostered by providing individuals with greater means of control over their own data, and data stewardship efforts provide an apt vehicle for doing so. Data stewards are independent intermediaries who lie between data generators (citizens), data collectors (fiduciaries), and data requestors (users of data). Stewards play a multi-dimensional role by unlocking the societal value of data and empowering individuals/communities to participate in the data economy while safeguarding their rights. We have witnessed other data stewarding initiatives around the world, including the Helsinki Region Infosphere, the Transport Data Collaborative in Seattle, and in the Brainport Smart District. This paper attempts to examine these, and other initiatives, to (a) highlight case studies of successful, equitable and beneficial private sector use of public sector (personal) data; (b) identify the modalities through which use of public sector data can generate greater public trust and benefit; and (c) distill important enablers necessary to foster such stewardship initiatives. Additionally, the paper will also look at other examples of stewardship of public goods, such as the Trust Ports of Scotland, for learnings to enable sustainable data stewardship models. We believe that these findings will be of relevance to the Scottish government as it looks to obtain greater use of public sector data.

The first section of this paper will provide an introduction to data stewardship and the landscape of sharing data for public good in the context of urban governance. The second section of this paper will provide an analysis of existing stewardship initiatives that work to make public sector (personal) data available for private use as well as initiatives that make privately collected data available for public use in the context of urban governance. While our initial scoping has identified a predominance of initiatives that work to improve urban mobility, the analysis in this section will cover models that work on various aspects of urban governance. Based on the analysis in section 2, the third section of this paper will distill policy principles necessary to encourage the growth and development of such initiatives as well as identify the key concomitants for use of public sector data in a manner that generates greater public trust and benefit.